

When Creativity Meets Spirituality: Unveiling the Rock Engravings of Bhagalpur, Bihar

Dr. Arabinda Singha Roy

Assistant Professor, Maulana Abul Kalam Azad University of Technology, West Bengal.

arabindasingharoy@gmail.com

Accepted: 20 Dec 2024 / Published online: 31 December 2024

Abstract

In ancient Indian culture, religion and creativity were deeply intertwined, with cultural expressions rarely existing independent of religious influence. Rock engravings, the focus of this study, represent a fascinating and thought-provoking aspect of this cultural synergy. These engravings are typically found on the surfaces of hillocks or scattered rocks and often reflect religious themes. The two primary sites examined in this study, Dhol Pahari and Gauri Pahari, are particularly rich in such engravings, most of which are closely tied to religious beliefs and practices. While a few engravings may appear less explicitly religious, they cannot be entirely divorced from the pervasive influence of faith. This article seeks to present a comprehensive analysis of these creative expressions, highlighting their gradual evolution and assimilation into the religious landscape of ancient India.

Key Words: Bhagalpur, Gauripur, Dholpahari, Engraving, Religious, Creativity.

Introduction

Religious expression and creative endeavor have historically coexisted in ancient Indian culture, often serving as two sides of the same coin. Cultural artifacts devoid of religious influence are both rare and sporadic. Art, as a manifestation of human creativity, provides a canvas for the depiction of idealistic and spiritual individuality. Throughout history, humanity has etched and carved materials, transforming inert objects into powerful symbols of their inner aspirations. Sometimes, this creative impulse has given rise to iconometric sculptures, while at other times, entire rock surfaces have been converted into intricate three-dimensional pictorial narratives. Rarer still are rock surfaces etched with engravings that convey the artist's transcendental revelations and epiphanies.

In India, the symbiotic relationship between art and religion has been a cornerstone of cultural identity since time immemorial. Artistic endeavors unmoored from religious themes hold little resonance in the Indian subcontinent. During a field expedition conducted in 2017–18 within the Bhagalpur district, nearly two hundred iconographic figurines representing various pantheons were documented. Without exception, these carvings reflect profound religious inspiration. Among these artistic creations, this article focuses exclusively on the engravings unearthed in select locales within the Commissionerate of Bhagalpur, highlighting their historical and cultural significance.

Sites of Discovery

The engravings under discussion have been recovered not only from locations within the current administrative boundaries of Bhagalpur district but also from regions lying along its borders. These

areas, though geographically external to the present-day district, historically belonged to the erstwhile Commissionerate of Bhagalpur. The notable sites of discovery include:

Figure 2: Map illustrating the major sites where engravings have been documented.

1. Gauri Pahadi (Gauri Hillock):

Gauri Pahadi, a modest and isolated hillock, is located on the southern fringe of the Kharagpur Hills—a typology of landform commonly encountered within the Bhagalpur district (Figure 2). This particular hillock is situated in Gauripur village, under the Shambhuganj subdivision of Banka district, which historically formed part of the Bhagalpur Commissionerate in Bihar. Geographically, the site lies approximately 26.56 km northwest of Banka town and 46.95 km southwest of Bhagalpur town. The village spans an area of 56 hectares and is home to a modest population of 178 residents.

The hillock itself is essentially an aggregation of granite block stones, appearing unassuming at first glance. A narrow stream meanders between Gauripur village and the hillock, adding a natural element of separation. On the northern periphery of the village stands a newly constructed temple, housing an image of **Umamaheshvaramurti** (Figure 2.1 A). Adjacent to the temple, scattered large granite blocks can be observed, arranged in a seemingly random manner, and it is on these stones that the engravings have been identified.

Approximately 160 meters to the east of this temple, another cluster of granite blocks is found. The surface of these stones bears three engraved stupas accompanied by an inscriptive line, attributed to the 13th–14th century. The inscription is underlined, lending it a distinctive

appearance. These engravings and the inscription represent invaluable historical artifacts, shedding light on the artistic and religious practices of the era.

Figure 2.1 A: Image of Umamahesvaramurti, Gauripur, Banka.

1.I. Stupas 1, 2, and 3:

These images are meticulously carved on the surface of a substantial granite block, showcasing all the architectural components typically associated with a fully realized stupa. Each stupa is set atop a prominent, double-layered plinth (*medhi*), providing an elevated and sturdy base. Rising from the plinth, the cylindrical *anda* forms the central structure, adorned with intricate mouldings.

**Figure 2.1. I. a. Engraved Stupa 1,
Gauripur, Banka.**

Specifically, five mouldings embellish the lower portion of the *anda*, while three additional mouldings are distinctly positioned at its midpoint.

Crowning the *anda* is a circular *harmika*, from which the central *yasti* (spire) ascends. Atop the *yasti*, a seven-tiered *chhatra* (umbrella) is prominently erected, symbolizing spiritual elevation. Further enhancing the architectural complexity, an eight-spoked wheel is positioned at the apex of the stupa. Between the wheel and the *chhatra*, a flying *dhvaja* (banner) is depicted, its elegant form extending downward to the midpoint of the *anda*.

Remarkably, all three stupas exhibit uniformity in their architectural elements, reflecting a shared design language. At the base of each stupa, a four-line inscription is present, although it has been significantly blurred over time, rendering its content indiscernible. The average height of these stupas is approximately 1 meter, demonstrating their modest yet intricate construction (Figure 2.1. Ia, b, and c).

Figure 2.1. I. b. Engraved Stupa 2, Gauripur, Banka.

Figure 2.1. I. c. Engraved Stupa 3,

Gauripur, Banka.

2.1.II. Stupas 4, 5, and 6:

Approximately 50 meters west of the present temple, a large granite block has been identified, bearing three distinct depictions on its surface. Structurally, these representations closely resemble the previously described stupas (Stupas 1, 2, and 3), exhibiting the same fundamental architectural elements. However, they differ in scale, with each stupa displaying variations in height.

Stupa 5 measures 75 cm in height, Stupa 6 stands at 82 cm, and Stupa 7 reaches 93 cm. Despite their differences in dimensions, all three stupas retain the key architectural components integral to their design: a well-defined *medhi* (plinth), a cylindrical *anda*, a circular *harmika*, a *yasti* (spire), a multi-tiered *chhatra* (umbrella), and a flowing *dhvaja* (banner). These elements are meticulously positioned, reflecting an adherence to traditional iconometric principles.

Notably, unlike the earlier stupas, these depictions lack any accompanying inscriptions. Their absence, however, does not diminish their artistic and architectural coherence, as the stupas remain exemplary representations of the craftsmanship and religious symbolism of their era (Figure 2.1.II).

Figure 2.1. II. Engraved Stupa no. 4, 5, and 6.

2.1.III. Stupas 7, 8, and 9:

Approximately 30 meters north of the temple, another granite block has been discovered, featuring engraved stupas on its exposed surface. These stupas, though similar in design to the previously described examples, present challenges in detailed assessment. Their heights and specific features remain indeterminate, as some of the engravings are significantly blurred, and a substantial portion of the stone block remains buried beneath the earth.

Despite these limitations, the visible elements suggest that these stupas adhere to the architectural conventions expected of a complete stupa. The faintly discernible outlines hint at the presence of integral components such as the *medhi* (plinth), *anda* (dome), *harmika* (railing), *yasti* (spire), *chhatra* (umbrella), and possibly a *dhvaja* (banner), though further excavation and analysis would be required to confirm these features in detail (Figure 2.1.III).

Figure 2.1. III. Engraved Stupa no. 7, 8, and 9.

2.1.IV. Inscriptions and Additional Discoveries:

As previously mentioned, inscriptions have been identified at specific locations (Figure 2.1.IV).

These inscriptions consist of two horizontal lines, one positioned directly below the other, accompanied by an additional separate line situated a few centimeters to the right of the primary inscription.

In addition to these inscriptions, two more engraved stupas have been discovered on a stone block approximately 70 meters north of the current temple. Although their design is consistent with the architectural features described earlier, the engravings are severely weathered, rendering their details indistinct and challenging to interpret. These findings underscore the historical and artistic significance of the site, despite the limitations imposed by time and environmental degradation.

Figure 2.1. IV: Inscription engraved on a block of stone.

2. Dhol Pahari:

Dhol Pahari is a modest hillock, akin to the Gauri Hill of Banka, located in the village of Dholpahari Milik. This village spans an area of 174 hectares and is home to a population of 773 individuals (Figure 2). Presently, the village falls under the jurisdiction of the Asarganj subdivision within the Munger district, part of the Bhagalpur Commissionerate in Bihar. The hillock lies approximately 350 meters south of the village and assumes the shape of a lozenge or rhombus.

Atop the hillock stands a temple, believed to be no more than a century old. However, enshrined within the *garbhagriha* of the temple is a finely crafted figurine of a Naga-purusha (Figure 2.2.A). Adjacent to the temple, a platform is visible, which likely marks the foundation of a ruined temple. The bricks of the plinth measure approximately 39 x 22 x 7 cm and are bound with mud mortar.

Figure 2.2. A: Naga-Purusha, Dholpahari, Munger, Bihar.

The hillock itself features two distinct peaks, separated by a natural depression that forms a striking visual contrast.

At the foothill of the peak crowned by the temple, a mound is observed, rising 5 meters above the surrounding terrain. One side of this mound is exposed, revealing a brick wall joined with mud mortar. It is noteworthy that the dimensions of the bricks in this wall are identical to those of the bricks measured at the platform atop the hillock.

The hillock itself is remarkable in its form. The eastern slope is strewn with granite boulders and descends gently, merging seamlessly with the foothill below. By contrast, the western slope exhibits a strikingly unique profile. Here, the incline abruptly breaks from the summit, descending steeply to meet the foothill in a near-vertical drop (Figure 2.2.B). This abrupt slope forms a spur-like feature with a broad rocky surface, upon which numerous engravings are found.

These engravings include depictions of stupas as well as various figurines, showcasing the site's historical and cultural significance.

Figure 2.2. B. General view of the Dholpahari.

2.1. Engraved Stupas

On the western side of the hill, a total of nine engraved stupas have been discovered. The rock surface here forms an abrupt slope, which often experiences runoff during rains. A layer of patina overlays the rock surface, obscuring the engravings. Upon carefully removing this patina, the stupas were revealed. Morphologically, these stupas vary significantly from one another. Seven prominent examples, differing in size and detail, are described below:

2.1.A. Engraved Stupa I

This stupa is located on the western face of the hill. It stands 75 cm in height and measures 46 cm in width. The structure rests upon a plinth, delineated by a series of etched lines. Rising from the plinth is the main cylindrical body of the stupa. Atop this cylindrical structure is a *Harmika*, upon which a *Dhvaja* (flag) appears to be fluttering (Figure 2.2.1.A).

Figure 2.2.1 A: Engraved Stupa I.

Figure 2.2.1 B: Engraved Stupa B.

2.1.B. Engraved Stupa II

This stupa is also engraved on the same surface as the previous one. In this depiction, a *medhi* (platform) is faintly discernible, though not entirely clear. From the *medhi* emerges an apsidal *anda* (dome), prominently projected. Along the middle of the *anda*, three mounds are visible, crafted through precise etchings.

Atop the *anda* rests a circular *harmika*, from which rises a *yasti* (spire). This *yasti* supports both a *chhatra* (parasol) and a *dhvaja* (flag). Within the central portion of the stupa, a seated **figure is** depicted in the *vajrasana* posture, with hands folded one upon the other, resting upon the lap (Figure 2.2.1.B).

Figure 2.2.1 C. Engraved Stupa III:

Figure 2.2.1 D. Engraved Stupa IV:

2.1.C. Engraved Stupa III

This engraving closely resembles the figure described in Section 2.2.1.A. Here, the *medhi* is depicted through a series of etched lines, upon which rests a cylindrical *anda*. The other components of the stupa—namely the *harmika*, *yasti*, *chhatra*, and *dhvaja*—are positioned in the same sequential order as described earlier (Figure 2.2.1.C).

2.1.D. Engraved Stupa IV

In this engraving, the plinth of the stupa is not clearly visible. Above the indistinct plinth, an apsidal *anda* is positioned. Atop the *anda* rests a circular *harmika*, from which rises a *yasti* supporting a *chhatra*. However, the *dhvaja* in this instance is not distinctly visible. Additionally, a two-line inscription is observed on the surface of the stupa, which appears to have been engraved at a later time (Figure 2.2.1.D).

Figure 2.2.1 E. Engraved Stupa V

Figure 2.2.1 F. Engraved Stupa VI

2.1.E. Engraved Stupa V

This engraving closely mirrors the figure described in Section 2.2.1.C. The *medhi* is depicted by etching the surface of the rock, upon which rests a cylindrical *anda*. Along the middle of the *anda*, a moulding comprised of three etched lines is clearly visible. Atop the *anda* stands a *harmika*, from which rises a *yasti*. The *yasti* supports a *chhatra*, to which a *dhvaja* is affixed (Figure 2.2.1.E).

2.1.F. Engraved Stupa VI

This stupa shares similarities with the previous example. It features an apsidal shape, positioned upon an *anda*. Atop the stupa are the sequential elements of a *harmika*, *yasti*, *chhatra*, and *dhvaja* (Figure 2.2.1.F).

2.2. Anthropomorphic Figures

In addition to the engraved stupas, several anthropomorphic figurines have been discovered on the same rock surface of the hillock where the stupas are located. These figurines may represent divine entities or may hold a more secular significance. Details of these engravings are provided below:

2.2.A. Engraved Figure I

On the western cliff of the hillock, on a rugged granite surface, a large engraved figurine measuring 1.8 meters in height and 1.6 meters in breadth has been discovered. This massive figure was initially concealed beneath a thick layer of patina. Upon carefully clearing the patina, the engraving came to light.

Figure 2.2.2. A. Engraved Figure I

The figure is robust and imposing in appearance. It possesses a bold facial expression, with two broad eyes accentuated by thick, arch-like eyebrows. It remains uncertain whether a third eye is present on its broad forehead. The eyeballs are distinctly positioned, aligned appropriately. A crown or turban seems to rest upon its curly and coiled long hair, which extends to the shoulders.

The neck is thick and adorned with two layers of intricately designed necklaces. Behind the head, a circular halo is etched, bordered by two deep incised lines. Two conical objects are depicted below the head, extending outward from the shoulders. The figure features a prominent pot belly, with the upper body uncovered and adorned with a *yajnopavita* (sacred thread).

The lower portion of the body is draped in a *dhoti*, depicted as reaching the knees. The right leg is extended and rests upon the left leg. The right arm is bent at the elbow and raised, holding a round object. Intriguingly, a stupa is carved into the raised hand, suggesting that this detail was likely

added after the primary figure was completed. The left hand rests upon the folded left leg in a *suchi hasta mudra* (gesture of pointing or precision).

The lower part of the figurine is not clearly visible. However, based on the carving, it can be surmised that the figure is seated on a highly ornate throne (Figure 2.2.2.A).

Figure 2.2.2. B. Engraved Figure II

On either side of the central figure, two additional figurines are depicted. The figurine to the left of the main figure appears to represent a female, though it is heavily blurred, rendering its details indistinguishable. Adjacent to this blurred figure, a smaller figure is depicted in a standing posture, seemingly holding a lotus in its right hand. However, this figure is also significantly blurred and difficult to discern.

The figurine to the right of the central figure is likewise in a standing posture. The upper part of this figure is not clearly visible, though its folded hands suggest an act of homage, likely directed

toward the central image. Beneath the main figure, a line of inscription in *Siddhamatrika* script is observed.

2.2.B. Engraved Figure II

A small figurine, measuring 57 cm in height, is engraved upon the rock surface on the western side of the hill. The figure is depicted in a standing posture, with one hand folded and raised to chest level. The features of the figurine are entirely blurred, rendering further details indistinct (Figure 2.2.2.B).

2.3. Other Engraved Features

In addition to the aforementioned engravings, several other symbols and features are depicted on the same rock surface. Some of these are purely symbolic representations, while others appear to be figurative or structural but remain too indistinct to be clearly understood. Their specific details are provided below:

Figure 2.2.3. A. Engraved Feature I:

Figure 2.2.3. B. Engraved Feature II

2.3. A. Engraved Feature I

This feature is depicted on the same side, situated not far from the large anthropomorphic figure. A total of three images of this type have been discovered. These images portray a conical-shaped structure with a semi-circular end, positioned on an elevated plinth. Two concave lines converge in the middle of the structure, forming a pointed apex from which a straight line extends downward to the base of the plinth. The five-tiered plinth is illustrated by etching its surface. Notably, the feature bears a closer resemblance to a Shiva linga rather than a stupa (Figure 2.2.3. A).

2.3. B. Engraved Feature II

This feature is distinct from those previously described. It depicts a *Chakra* positioned on a lofty plinth, which appears to be adorned with lotus petals. The plinth stands 35 cm in height and consists of two mouldings: one marked by three lines and the other by two. At the top edges of the plinth, two lotus petals are prominently displayed. Between these petals lies a wheel with eight spokes. This feature evokes the narrative of the *Dharmachakra Pravartana* (Figure 2.2.3. B).

Figure 2.2.3. C. Engraved Feature III

Figure 2.2.3. D. Engraved Feature IV

2.3. C. Engraved Feature III

Several circular features, formed by etching the surface, are observed on the western face of the hillock. More than ten similar features are present on the same surface. Their purpose and symbolic significance, however, remain unclear (Figure 2.2.3. C).

2.3. D. Engraved Feature IV

Although this feature cannot be strictly categorized as an engraving, it is carved on the rock surface within a semi-circular arch. The image exhibits a conical shape, bearing a stronger resemblance to a Shiva linga, though its similarity to a stupa cannot be entirely dismissed (Figure 2.2.3. D).

2.4. Inscriptions

In addition to the figurines and features mentioned above, more than ten inscriptions, often consisting of a few words, have been discovered. In several cases, these inscriptions are situated beneath the figurines or engraved stupas, while others appear sporadically across the rock surface.

3. Bamdeo:

Bamdeo is a small village encompassing an area of 195 hectares, with a population of 2,043. It lies 28.14 km south of Bhagalpur town and 21.15 km northeast of Banka town, situated within the C.D. Block of Rajaun in the Banka district of Bihar (Figure 2). A road bisects the village, and on the right side of this road, a broken image of the Buddha was found in front of a house.

This figure portrays the Buddha standing, with one hand in *varada mudra* (gesture of granting wishes) while the other hand is broken. The headless statue measures 45 cm in length. Beside his feet on the right side, a smaller figure is depicted with folded hands. On the reverse side of the figure, an image of a stupa is carved.

In this depiction, the *anda* (dome) of the stupa rests atop a high three-stepped *medhi* (platform), with each step delineated by moulding created through etching. The *anda* is apsidal in form and

includes a moulding in its midsection. Beneath the plinth, a four-line inscription in later Brahmi script is visible (Figure 2.3).

Figure 2.3: Image of Buddha, Bamdeo, Banka.

Methodology of the Analysis

For the analytical study of these creations, primary emphasis was placed on field surveys. Extensive and comprehensive fieldwork was conducted across the districts of Bhagalpur, Banka, and parts of the Munger district. During the surveys, each artifact and feature was meticulously examined and documented in detail. Measurements, photographs, and records of their locational significance were carefully compiled for every engraving.

The geology and geomorphology of the respective areas were also taken into account. Additionally, the demographic composition and population ratios of the regions were considered for the present study.

Following the fieldwork, the locations of all identified sites were accurately plotted on a map, and the relationships between these sites were systematically analyzed. Finally, a comparative study was undertaken, juxtaposing the engravings documented in the study area with similar engravings recorded in the peripheral regions.

An Analytical Study

The tradition of engraving on rock surfaces dates back to prehistoric times. Numerous examples of such engravings have been documented across the Indian subcontinent. The neighboring state of Jharkhand, which lies adjacent to the present study area, has evidence of similar engravings from the prehistoric period (Sinha and Singha Roy 2018, 81-87). These engravings have persisted over time, evolving in their thematic representations through successive eras.

With respect to the present study, the engravings are not older than the 10th–11th centuries CE, and some can be dated to the 13th–14th centuries CE. A few comparable engravings have also been reported from neighboring regions of the study area.

Recently, twenty such engravings were reported from Barki Pahari in the Lakhisarai district of Bihar (Figure 4.1) (Bhattacharya, Chattopadhyay, Kumar, and Mishra 2017, 195-204). Along the eastern slope of a hillock near a stupa, three engraved votive stupas of varying heights have been observed. One of these stupas includes an image of the Buddha in *bhumisparsha mudra*. A significant concentration of similar engraved votive stupas has been documented on the western slope of the hill, where a seated Buddha figure is prominently depicted in the center of the stupas (Figure 4.2). However, the authors did not provide any specific information regarding the period of these engravings.

In the Gilgit-Baltistan region of Pakistan, approximately 30,000 engravings and 5,000 graffiti have been discovered. While the majority of these were created during prehistoric times, some engravings, including stupas and Buddha images, date to the early medieval period.

An engraved image of Buddha has also been documented in an inscription found in the village of Janibigha, located six miles east of Bodh Gaya. In a field to the east of the village, an iron chain, fragments of images, and various relics were uncovered. Among these, a long stone bearing the inscription was buried under a date palm tree in a small patch of uncultivated land. The stone, made of grayish-black sandstone, is rectangular in section and resembles a boundary pillar. It measures 3 feet 1 inch in height, 9 inches in width, and 6 inches in thickness.

Figure 4.1. Engraved Stupa, Barki Pahari,
Lakhisarai (After Bhattacharya, *and all* 2017)

4.2. Engraved Stupa, Barki Pahari, Lakhisarai
(Photo courtesy of Dr. Rajat Sanyal)

The face bearing the inscription is finely dressed, except for an 11-inch section at the bottom that is rough-dressed, evidently to facilitate burial in the ground. The top of the stone is carved into a rough knob. The reverse side is hammer-dressed, while one side is chisel-dressed like the bottom. The inscription spans an area of 9 inches by 7 inches and consists of 14 lines of writing (Panday 1918, 274). Above the inscription is an engraved image of Buddha. This inscription is dated to the 13th century CE.

General Observations

Evidence of engravings has been identified at three locations within the Bhagalpur Commissionaire, situated in different directions.

At Dhol Pahari, located along the border of Bhagalpur and Munger districts, the terrain is undulating. Amidst vast agricultural fields, a prominent hillock can be observed standing in isolation. The landscape of Gauri Hill differs significantly; here, the land is similarly undulating but densely covered with jungle. The hill is notably high, with small streams flowing from its summit. This hillock covers a large area, and stone blocks are scattered over several kilometers.

The scenario at Bamdeo is distinct. According to local historians and informants, the image found here did not originally belong to the village but was likely brought from elsewhere. The village was reputedly known for anti-social activities in the past, including incidents of antiquity theft. Thus, the possibility of the image being transported from another location cannot be ruled out.

The engravings at Dhol Pahari differ stylistically from those at Gauri Hill. The engravings at Gauri Hill exhibit a degree of monotony, with all stupas sharing similar *anda* (dome) designs featuring distinct mouldings and high plinths. While cylindrical in form, the upper portions of these stupas are slightly apsidal, with a wider distance between the outer lines of the *anda*. These stupas are uniform in height and morphology, making differentiation challenging.

In contrast, the engravings at Dhol Pahari are smaller and more varied in morphology. They range from cylindrical to apsidal shapes and are depicted on lower plinths. Some stupas include an image of the Buddha at their center. Additionally, Dhol Pahari features

orthomorphic figurines and symbolic engravings, such as chakras flanked by two wheels and representations resembling Shiva lingas—features absent from other locations.

The engraving on the reverse side of the Buddha image at Bamdeo bears similarities to the stupas at Gauri Hill.

As mentioned earlier, in India, art and religion have been deeply intertwined since ancient times. Artistic creations often serve religious purposes, and these engravings are no exception. Their appearance, stylistic features, and associated elements strongly suggest a religious rather than social intent.

At Gauri Hill, the engraved stupas were accompanied by two inscriptions and a single image at the foothill. This image, identified as *Umamahesvaramurti* and likely dating to the 10th–11th centuries CE, appears unrelated to the stupas. While some scholars, such as Satish Sinha in his monograph *Ahouta-Gauripur: Khoj abang Chintan*, have argued that these engravings represent Shiva lingas, others have sought to associate them with Jain traditions.

Conversely, at Dhol Pahari, the engraved stupas, anthropomorphic figurines, and symbolic depictions seem more informative regarding their purpose. The Buddha image engraved within some stupas, as well as parallels with similar engravings at Barki Pahari in Lakhisarai, support the theory that these engravings are connected to the Buddhist pantheon. The depiction of stupas as objects of worship or offerings is further corroborated by the Janibigha inscription and the engravings from Gilgit-Baltistan. Dating these engravings presents significant challenges. At Gauri Hill, no conclusive evidence for dating has been discovered. An inscription adjacent to the rock surface with

three engravings is dated to no earlier than the 12th century CE. However, this inscription is not directly related to the stupas and could have been engraved earlier or later.

At Dhol Pahari, numerous inscriptions accompany the stupas and figurines, but some letters appear to have been engraved over existing figurines and stupas, suggesting a later addition. However, inscriptions found on the back of the Buddha image and at the plinth of one stupa can be directly linked to the engravings. Palaeographic analysis dates these inscriptions to the 7th–9th centuries CE, and the associated stupas and images are likely from the same period.

The Janibigha inscription also provides a strong basis for dating, supported by evidence from Gilgit-Baltistan. Archaeological remains are scarce at the mentioned sites. At Gauri Hill, only a few fragments of red ware, possibly from the early medieval period, have been found. The mound at the foothill and the brick remains at the summit of the temple at Dhol Pahari are notable. The bricks resemble those from early medieval structures, and pottery fragments, primarily bowls, bear resemblance to shallow bowls with inverted rims from the same period.

No artifacts have been recovered with the Bamdeo image. However, a nearby village, Jhitka, yielded a significant number of Black-and-Red Ware (BRW) pieces.

It is evident that settlements existed near the sites where these engravings were discovered. These engravings likely served specific religious purposes, probably associated with the Buddhist pantheon, and were created between the 7th and 13th centuries CE.

References

Bhattacharya, G., Chattopadhyay, R. K., Kumar, A., & Mishra, N. K. (2017). Archaeological investigation at Uren (Urain), District Lakhisarai, Bihar. *Puratattva*, **2017**, 195–204.

Panday, H. (1918). The Janibigha inscription. *Bihar and Odisha Research Society*, **1918**, 274.

Sinha, C. P. A. S. (2018). *Prehistory and protohistory of Jharkhand*. Delhi: B.R. Publishing Corporation.

Sinha Roy, A. (2020). *Sculpture in the State Museum, Ranchi*. Delhi: B.R. Publishing Corporation.

